

and finally dried *in vacuo* at 100°. The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) confirm the 1 : 1 stoichiometry for metal-ligand.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complex	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)	
	Metal	N
[Ni(DTTHD)](ClO ₄) ₂	7.30 (7.49)	7.00 (7.15)
[Cu(DTTHD)](ClO ₄) ₂	7.62 (7.51)	6.97 (7.14)
[Co(DTTHD)](ClO ₄) ₂	7.94 (8.05)	7.04 (7.10)

Results and Discussion

The electronic spectrum of the ligand recorded in benzene solvent, indicated two peaks at 27 100 and 38 910 cm⁻¹, and the molar extinction coefficient was found to be 3 651 cm⁻¹ mol⁻¹. These bands are assigned to the transitions $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, respectively. The ir spectra of the ligand showed very strong absorptions at 1 670 (C=O) and at 1 630 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The weak band due to C—H stretch is observed at 3 040 cm⁻¹. The medium absorptions appearing in the region 1 580-1 600 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the combination of C=C and C=N frequencies. The disappearance of the free NH₂ absorption of the starting material coupled with the analytical data has confirmed that the 2 : 1 condensation of the hydrazone with the acetylacetone has indeed taken place.

The nmr spectrum of the ligand recorded in CDCl₃/TMS showed aromatic multiplets in the region δ 7.2-8.0 and methyl and methylene signals at δ 1.66 and 2.06, respectively. This is in accordance with the values expected from the ligands of similar type⁹. The mass spectrum exhibited the molecular ion peak (*M*⁺) at *m/z* 526, thus supporting the proposed molecular formula for the ligand.

The metal chelate obtained from this ligand are expected to be quite stable as in the case of Schiff base complexes derived from acetylacetone due to the polarisation of ligand electrons and the formation of M-L π -bond.

The conductance values (125-150 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹) of all the complexes in DMF show their 2 : 1 electrolyte nature¹⁰. The magnetic moments obtained by Gouy method give a clue to the nature of the stereochemistry around the metal ions. The nickel(II) complex was found to be paramagnetic with a magnetic moment of 3.2 B.M., while copper(II) complex showed a value of 1.8 B.M. The esr spectra recorded for the microcrystalline copper(II) and cobalt(II) complexes at room temperature show $g_{11}=2.218$, $g_2=2.048$, $A_{11}=170 \times 10^{-4}$ cm⁻¹ and $g_1=2.348$; and $g_3=2.075$, respectively.

The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMF solution. A broad band at 20 833 cm⁻¹ characteristic for the square-planar

nickel(II) complexes has been observed in the case of [Ni(DTTHD)](ClO₄)₂, while [Cu(DTTHD)](ClO₄)₂ and [Co(DTTHD)](ClO₄)₂ showed broad bands at 16 500 and 15 750 cm⁻¹, respectively. A distorted planar geometry can be envisaged for these complexes.

The ir spectra of the complexes indicate a positive shift of 10-15 cm⁻¹ in the case of both C=O and C=N frequencies, thus confirming the N₂O₂ coordination in these complexes. The perchlorate absorption in the 1 100 cm⁻¹ region is also observed.

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Complexes of *p*-Chlorophenyloxythiosemicarbazide with Manganese(II), Iron(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II)

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THE ligands having —N—C=S group with nitrogen and sulphur as donor sites have been the subject of two reviews^{1,2}. Thiosemicarbazide exists in two tautomeric forms I and II^{3,4}. As the

chelating behaviour of *p*-chlorophenylalxythiosemicarbazide has not been reported so far, its extensive studies are needed. The present paper reports the preparation of some new complexes of bivalent Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Cd and Hg. The complexes have been characterised with the help of ir, uv-visible, magnetic susceptibility and analytical data.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The ligand was prepared by the reported method⁵.

Preparation of complexes (C₁₆H₁₄Cl₂N₆O₅S₂) M(II).xH₂O: An aqueous solution of MCl₂.xH₂O (1 mmol) was mixed with a solution of ligand (1 mmol) in DMF with continuous stirring and digested on steam-bath for 1 h. The solid product precipitated was washed with water and dried in vacuum.

The complexes are insoluble in most organic solvents. However, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺ and Cu²⁺ complexes are soluble in DMF. All the complexes decompose above 280°.

Elemental analysis data are given in Table 1. Infrared spectra (KBr) of the ligand and the complexes in the range 4000-200 cm⁻¹, were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 521 spectrophotometer, and electronic spectra (nujol) of the complexes were obtained in the range 200-900 nm with a Carry 14 spectrophotometer from I.I.T., Kanpur. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined with the help of Faraday balance at room temperature using ferrous ammonium sulphate as the standard.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry ML has been established for all the complexes from the results of elemental analysis. Upon coordination through N-H group, the band at 3320 and 3100 cm⁻¹ either disappeared or became broad in all the complexes, showing coordination of metal ion through NH group. A strong band at 1670 cm⁻¹ becomes broad and weak, which further suggest contribution of δ_{NH} in coordination. Band at 1580 or 1540 cm⁻¹ either disappear or becomes broad and weak in all the complexes, showing the chelation through -N-C=S moiety (thioamide band I)^{6,7}. The assignment of the vibrational modes at 1360, 1250, 1150 and 750 cm⁻¹ is summarised in Table 2. A band at 830 cm⁻¹ disappears in all the complexes showing the contribution of δ(-N-N-C-). Bands at 540

and 450 cm⁻¹ disappear in all the complexes, showing the contribution of τ(N-N). Two new bands at 500 and 370 cm⁻¹ appear in all the complexes showing the presence of ν(M-N) and ν(M-S), respectively.

Effective magnetic moment of the Cu²⁺ complex was found in the normal range 1.88 B.M. The uv-visible spectrum shows three bands at 34482, 35211 and 25000 cm⁻¹. The former two bands are charge transfer band of high energy, and the band at 25000 cm⁻¹ may be assigned as d-d transition, ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} for square-planar Cu²⁺ complex.

In the case of Fe²⁺ complex observed value of magnetic moment is found to be 5.27 B.M. In uv-visible spectra, the bands at 34482 and 21551 cm⁻¹ correspond to charge-transfer band and d-d transition, respectively. The band at 21551 cm⁻¹ can be assigned as ²A_{1g} → ²B_{1g} in the square-planar complex of Fe²⁺.

The observed value of magnetic moment in Mn complex is found to be 4.90 B.M. indicating the

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA FOR *p*-CHLOROPHENYLOXALYLTHIOSEMICARBAZIDE-METAL COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)					Decomp. temp. °C	Magnetic moment B.M.
		C	H	N	S	M		
L	White	43.23 (42.01)	3.80 (3.06)	19.33 (18.38)	19.22 (19.01)	—	200 ^a	—
[MnL].2H ₂ O	White	35.82 (35.04)	2.83 (2.55)	16.12 (15.33)	12.18 (11.68)	10.32 (10.02)	283	4.90
[FeL].4H ₂ O	Dark bluish green	33.01 (32.82)	2.85 (2.39)	14.60 (14.36)	11.21 (10.94)	10.72 (9.55)	282	5.27
[CoL.2H ₂ O].H ₂ O	Dark green	34.41 (32.73)	3.44 (2.63)	14.94 (14.73)	12.40 (11.23)	10.80 (10.34)	284	4.80
[NiL.2H ₂ O]	Yellowish green	35.02 (34.80)	3.11 (2.53)	14.11 (15.22)	12.29 (11.60)	11.37 (10.64)	290	2.84
[CuL].4H ₂ O	Reddish brown	33.10 (32.40)	2.85 (2.36)	14.37 (14.18)	11.50 (10.82)	12.02 (10.72)	285	1.88
[CdL].3H ₂ O	White	31.60 (30.79)	2.85 (2.25)	14.71 (13.522)	11.74 (10.26)	19.90 (18.03)	284	—
[HgL].2H ₂ O	Yellow	28.40 (27.68)	2.02 (2.01)	11.19 (12.11)	10.98 (9.22)	29.80 (28.90)	287	—

^aM.p.

TABLE 2—ASSIGNMENTS AND SHIFTS OF IR BANDS (CM⁻¹) OF THE LIGAND AND COMPLEXES

Ligand	Complex	Assignments	Shifts in the frequency and change in intensity
3 320m	—	In ligand due to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ asym and $\nu(\text{N-H})$ sym	Disappears or broadening
3 100m	—		Disappears or broadening
1 670s I	1670 $\pm$ 10	Contribution of $\delta(\text{NH})$	Broadening of $\delta(\text{N-H})$ band
1 580m I	—	Chelation through N=C-S moiety thioamide band I	Disappears or becomes broad
1 540m I	—		
1 360m II	1360 $\pm$ 10	Coordination through N=C-S and contribution of thioamide band II	Shifting by 10 cm ⁻¹
1 250m	1250-20	Showing the election drift from N-N(azide) band	Shifts to lower wave number
1 150m III	1150 $\pm$ 10	Coordination through NCS group, band III	
830w	—	Contribution of $\delta(\text{N-N-C-})$	Disappears
750w IV	—	Coordination through (C-S) group, band IV	Disappears
540m	—	Contribution of $\tau(\text{N-N})$	Disappears
450m	—	Contribution of $\tau(\text{N-N})$	Disappears
	500	$\nu(\text{M-N})$	
	340+30	$\nu(\text{M-S})$	

possibility of spin-free configuration ($b_{1g}^2 e_g^2 a_{1g}^1 b_{1g}^1$). Orbital configuration to the magnetic moment in square-planar complexes, is expected to be small as orbital angular momentum among the d-orbital is largely quenched by low symmetry D_{4h} . Thus the absence of transition band and the value of magnetic moment (4.90 B.M.) suggest square-planar arrangement of the ligand around Mn^{2+} ion.

The observed value of magnetic moment 2.84 B.M., suggests the presence of two unpaired electron in Ni^{2+} complex. There are bands at 31 250, 37 593, 20 576 and 19 230 cm⁻¹ in the electronic spectrum of Ni^{2+} complex. Bands at 31 250 and 37 593 cm⁻¹ may be due to charge-transfer band. The band at (486 nm) 20 576 cm⁻¹ suggest the existence of ground state ${}^3A_{2g}$ for octahedral Ni^{2+} complex¹⁰. Because the ratio of the frequencies 20 576 to 19 230 cm⁻¹ is found to be more sensitive to give the free ion value of $B' 616$ cm⁻¹ compared to the reported value of $B 1 080$ cm⁻¹ for Ni^{2+} complex⁹. The band at 20 576 (ν_2) and 19 230 cm⁻¹ (ν_1) can be assigned due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\text{P})$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\text{F})$ transitions for Ni^{2+} octahedral complex. The value of $10 Dq$ is found to be 20 328 cm⁻¹ which is extremely high compared to the reported value 12 000 cm⁻¹ for ethylenediamine for octahedral Ni^{2+} complex⁹.

The value of magnetic moment observed in the Co^{2+} complex 4.80 B.M., suggest the octahedral geometry of the complex⁹. There are two bands in the electronic transition at 20 408 and 18 867 cm⁻¹. The bands at 20 408 and 18 867 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(\text{P})$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transitions. The ratio of frequencies 20 408 to 18 867 cm⁻¹ is found to be more sensitive to give the free ion value of $B' 739$ cm⁻¹, compared to the reported value of $B 1 120$ cm⁻¹ for Co^{2+} complex.

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Thermodynamic Stability of some Rare Earths Complexes with Tyrosine. A Polarographic Study

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VARIOUS complexing reagents have been employed in the polarographic determination of rare earths¹⁻⁶. In continuation, the author now reports the thermodynamic stability of Ce^{3+} ,